

Conference Abstract

Biodiversity of Early Holocene large mammals from the territory of Bulgaria according to remains from archaeological sites

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Abstract

Animal remains from archeological sites give a rather good sample of data, showing habitats and biodiversity during the early Holocene . In multiple settlements in the Eastern Balkans, there are numerous remains of wild mammals that were hunted by humans through the prehistory (7200-5800 BP). This gives a general idea of the habitats around and near the settlements. Such deposits of animal remains are the main source of data on fauna during this period and give us information on the processes leading to the extinction of some species.

This paper analyzes more than 26000 animal remains (bones, horns, antlers and teeth) from large mammals from orders: Artiodactyla, Perissodactyla and Carnivora from 4 still unpublished deposits from Bulgaria. I summarize data from already published remains from 33 sites in East Balkans. These analyses provide a general picture of both habitats and biodiversity and some of the major factors that caused extinction of some large mammals in Bulgaria during the early Holocene.

Keywords

animal remains, prehistory, subfossil, bones, habitat

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